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Remission of uncontrolled type 2 diabetes mellitus in a patient treated with tumor necrosis factor-inhibitor: A case report

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Abstract

Biological agents that have recently been an important treatment of choice for ankylosing spondylitis due to the reduction of inflammation of the axial skeleton and joints through tumor necrosis factor blockade, have multiple therapeutic and adverse side effects. Out of all the side effects reported, one of the underexplored potential therapeutic side effects is remission of diabetes. We report a case of a diabetic Caucasian woman who developed continued glycemic control after treatment with a tumor necrosis factor-alpha inhibitor, etanercept. Additionally, we present a graphical account of fluctuations of glycosylated Hemoglobin (HbA1c) and C-reactive protein associated with etanercept treatment, and we provide a detailed discussion of the implications of this therapeutic side effect. Health care professionals need to be aware of the potentially therapeutic side effect of tumor necrosis factor-alpha inhibitors and should exercise caution when using it in conjunction with exogenous insulin and or oral hypoglycemic drugs. Randomized double blind controlled studies need to assess the efficacy of biologic agents as a potential treatment against type 2 diabetes especially in those individuals with inflammatory arthritis.

Keywords

Ankylosing Spondylitis, Etanercept, Tumor Necrosis Factor-Alpha Inhibitor, Diabetes, Rheumatic Diseases, Inflammatory

1. Introduction

Biologic agents have become the drug of choice in many inflammatory arthritic conditions. In rheumatoid arthritis, ankylosing spondylitis, psoriatic arthritis, or seronegative spondyloarthropathies, when traditional disease-modifying anti-rheumatic drugs (DMARDs) like methotrexate do not adequately control the disease process, TNF- α inhibitors like etanercept are utilized to block the actions of this cytokine released by macrophages and lymphocytes^[1,3]. Rheumatologists traditionally monitor disease severity of rheumatic diseases through joint pain, level of systemic involvement, and through presence of biomarkers like C-reactive protein (CRP). Researchers have established that TNF stimulates the liver to produce CRP among other biomarkers^[2]. The specific mechanism of action of this biologic agent is that it emulates the inhibitory effects of the

soluble TNF receptors. The inhibitory effect is enhanced by the property of the fusion protein which prolongs the presence in the bloodstream. Several major randomized control trials have demonstrated the efficacy of biologic agents in successful control of rheumatological diseases^[4-6].

Despite the significant success in treating inflammatory autoimmune rheumatic conditions, there are side effects that are associated with etanercept. Infusion reactions, tuberculosis, opportunistic fungal infections, and cancer remain as part of a list of documented side effects^[7-8]. Even though the inflammatory etiology of diabetes and other metabolic syndrome components has been elucidated, the precise effect of TNF- α blockers on these complex diseases are unknown. Blockade of inflammation is an aspect that has been previously investigated by many scientists, the potential therapeutic side effect of etanercept as a hypoglycemic agent has not been explored thoroughly. It has long been

demonstrated that TNF- α is positively correlated with insulin resistance in mice [9-10]. However, the research demonstrating the possible link between etanercept and glycemic control is scant.

2. Case Report

We report the case of a 45-year-old Caucasian woman with a history of Ankylosing Spondylitis (AS) who was initially treated with hydroxychloroquine. Additionally, she developed type 2 diabetes mellitus with postprandial venous glucose readings peaking at 304 mg/dL. Since her AS was not adequately controlled, additional treatment with TNF inhibitor etanercept at 50 mg subcutaneously weekly was started in January of 2012. Subsequently, her HbA1c levels dropped from 8% to 7% in six months after starting treatment as shown in Figure 1. During this time period, she did not take any other diabetes medications. Her HbA1c remained lower than the initial level, in the two years of followup.

Fig. 1. Fluctuations in HbA1c and corresponding estimated average glucose after commencing treatment with Etanercept on January of 2012. Dates are provided in month/date/year format.

Fig. 2. Fluctuations in levels of C-reactive protein after commencing treatment with etanercept on January of 2012. Dates are provided in month/date/year format.

In July and August of 2013, her etanercept was discontinued due to concerns of infection following open shoulder surgery. This correlates to the slight rise in HbA1c, as seen in Fig. 1. After a gap for 2 months, treatment with etanercept, at 50 mg subcutaneously weekly was reconvened

in September of 2013. Subsequently, within five months her HbA1c dropped from 7.1% to 6.4%. Her postprandial glucose readings peaked at 144 mg/dL. Overall, she developed two time periods when etanercept brought her diabetes under remission. She did not have any episodes of hypoglycemia or corresponding symptoms. She did not experience any major changes in body mass index (BMI) during this time period.

In order to monitor her disease process from AS, the CRP was drawn periodically. The CRP blood test results are provided in Figure 2 from February 2012 to June 2014. The patient had stopped taking etanercept in July and August of 2013 explaining the delayed increase in CRP at the end of 2013.

3. Discussion

Etanercept and other TNF- α inhibitors like adalimumab and golimumab are some biologic agents that are being utilized either individually or in conjunction with classic DMARDs for treatment, when treatment with the first-line DMARDs fail [1,3]. Due to effective blockade of TNF- α by mimicking soluble TNF receptors, this class of medications have shown to be effective against ankylosing spondylitis, psoriatic arthritis, rheumatoid arthritis, and ulcerative colitis [4-6]. While the biologic agents have proved to be successful in treating rheumatologic conditions there are potentially therapeutic side effects like glycemic control in diabetic patients.

According to the literature, ten patients were shown to individually have spurious hypoglycemic episodes after taking TNF- α inhibitors [11]. Even though the average time that it took to have a hypoglycemic reading since commencement of a TNF- α inhibitor was 4.3 months, one patient had a hypoglycemic reading within a month. Even though our patient did not report any hypoglycemic episodes, adequate glycemic control was achieved in 6 months, dropping HbA1c levels by 1%. In another pilot study, ten children with type 1 diabetes demonstrated a 0.41 % decrease from baseline of HbA1c [12]. This study demonstrates the potential efficacy of etanercept in diabetes.

In another case report of a 72-year-old man, Cheung and Bryer-Ash [13] described a patient who had a history of chronic psoriasis and type 2 diabetes mellitus and developed episodes of hypoglycemia. After being treated with etanercept for a month, he had glucose readings of 60 mg/dL or less a few times a week. Throughout the next 16 months of treatment with etanercept, his physicians progressively decreased his insulin dose and then completely stopped it. Physicians started treating his diabetes with oral anti-glycemic agents exclusively with adequate control [13]. However, the patient experienced no more episodes of hypoglycemia. After 1.5 years of treatment, while his BMI remained unchanged, his fasting blood sugar levels improved.

Our patient did not have any major fluctuations in BMI. This implies that weight loss could not be attributed to greater glycemic control. Additionally, the fluctuations in CRP that followed closely with the variations in HbA1c demonstrated how this can be used as a potential biomarker to monitor

disease severity of diabetes. This association also demonstrates the potential importance of the inflammatory etiology of diabetes, especially in patients with rheumatic conditions. Even though the elevated CRP in December of 2013 did not correlate with the HbA1c of <7%, this discrepancy can be attributed to a delayed effect of not taking etanercept for 2 months.

Yazdani-Biuki and colleagues [13] demonstrated how prolonged use of infliximab can cause a therapeutic side effect of higher insulin sensitivity. As seen with the effect of etanercept in this patient, one patient was able to cease taking insulin therapy and found remission from diabetes. Repeated case reports of hypoglycemic states and increased glucose tolerance demonstrates the therapeutic potential of TNF- α inhibitors in diabetes. On the molecular level, through mouse models, TNF- α is known to downregulate GLUT-4 in adipose tissue [14-16]. Specifically, GLUT-4 is a transporter which allows for uptake of glucose into adipose tissue which is one mechanism through which glycemic control is achieved [17-18]. Additionally, TNF- α is known to be associated with Toll-like Receptors 2 and 4 and cytokines like interleukin-6 [19]. These findings have potential genetic and molecular implications in monitoring diabetes disease level.

While the effect on the glycemic aspect of metabolic syndrome is noteworthy, the effect on the cardiac aspect of metabolic syndrome requires further investigation due to the overlap between diabetes and cardiovascular disease. Even though the potential therapeutic side effect of glycemic control is self-evident, researchers have found mixed evidence of how TNF- α inhibitors affect cardiovascular disease. Dixon and colleagues [20] from the British Society of Rheumatology found that out of 8,670 patients those who positively responded to TNF- α inhibitors had a 60% reduced risk of Myocardial Infarction compared to those that did not respond. This demonstrates that addressing the inflammatory component addresses diabetes and cardiovascular disease. Researchers have also demonstrated that TNF- α inhibitors reduce formation of plaque and decrease aortic stiffness [21-24]. However, evidence also suggests that TNF- α inhibitors are responsible for exacerbating heart failure and decreasing cardiac compliance [25-26]. As demonstrated from previous research, caution must be practiced before determining the overall effect on heart disease.

This case report serves as a potential guide to investigate more thoroughly the potential therapeutic effect of TNF- α inhibitors in glycemic control. Health care professionals need to be aware of all of the side effects, especially the hypoglycemic effect, associated with TNF- α inhibitors. Without awareness, this potentially therapeutic side effect can have a detrimental effect of hypoglycemia, especially on individuals without diabetes. Along with other precautions like a baseline tuberculosis test, all patients need to have closely monitored blood sugar levels. Scientists and physicians need to perform randomized control trials in order to delineate the potential therapeutic role of TNF- α inhibitors on diabetes and other aspects of metabolic syndrome like cardiovascular disease.

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